

GROQ-SEQ PLATFORM

Technical Bulletin for GROQ-seq T7 RNA Polymerase Function Assay

A technical bulletin on the onboarding of a T7 RNA Polymerase (T7 RNAP) assay to the GROQ-seq platform.

- Provides technical overview of the assay produced in our original T7 RNAP proposal¹.
- Uses a gene circuit to tie T7 RNAP activity to bacterial cell growth.
- Produces quantitative functional measurements across an approximate 5-fold dynamic range.
- Measures 34,000 T7 RNAP variants, including more than 12,000 single- and 21,000 multi-residue mutants.

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Overview

The goal of this project was to develop a pooled, quantitative assay for measuring T7 RNA polymerase (T7 RNAP) function using the Growth-Based Quantitative Sequencing (GROQ-seq) platform². T7 RNAP's capacity to act as a signal transducer and amplifier, along with its remarkable processivity in RNA synthesis, makes it a particularly attractive target. It forms the basis for a wide variety of synthetic biology projects, such as in vitro mRNA production³, biosensor creation⁴, recombinant gene expression⁵, and gene-specific continuous mutagenesis⁶.

The assay described in this technical bulletin works by linking T7 RNAP function to cellular fitness. For this T7 RNAP data release, the function value is the level of transcriptional output from a T7 promoter due to the activity of a T7 RNAP variant. This is achieved using a plasmid where T7 RNAP activity modulates the expression of dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR). DHFR expression confers resistance to trimethoprim (TMP); therefore, changes in T7 RNAP function correlate with changes in TMP resistance, which can be measured as differences in cellular growth (fitness) across four timepoints. Function values are calculated using fitness measurements for samples with and without TMP. Variants measured in this assay are uniquely barcoded, enabling pooled sequencing-based measurement of relative fitness. Importantly, a barcoded ladder of calibration variants is included in every pool, allowing relative fitness measurements to be converted into quantitative functional values and ensuring reproducibility across experimental batches.

The pilot dataset generated by the GROQ-seq T7 RNAP assay can be accessed at data.alignbio.org. The pilot dataset generated quantitative T7 RNAP function data for two libraries: a site-saturation variant library (SSVL) and an error-prone PCR (epPCR) library (see the Dataset Description section for additional details). The long-term objective of generating these datasets is to enable the development of predictive models that can infer the effects of mutations on T7 RNAP function directly from protein sequence.

The assay described in this technical report currently supports T7 RNAP variants. The calibration ladder implemented in the pilot dataset resulted in sparse coverage of function to achieve single order of magnitude dynamic range. These measurements reveal biologically significant differences in function across thousands of T7 RNAP variants. Additional calibration variants can be mined from the dataset to expand coverage and improve calibration. In the future, this assay could also be readily extended to evaluate additional RNA polymerases, measure biophysical parameters of T7 transcription, or to systematically explore the impact of additional assay conditions, including antibiotic concentration and other environmental factors.

Assay Details

Assay Characteristics

- Produces quantitative functional measurements across a 5-fold change in transcriptional activity⁷.
- Biological reproducibility for T7 RNA polymerase variants was assessed by comparing measurements from independent barcodes corresponding to the same variants⁷. Comparing barcodes within a single condition illustrates moderate agreement between barcode pairs (A, Spearman $\rho = 0.710$, RMSE = 0.314)⁷.

Protocols

Prior to integration into the GROQ-seq, barcode-variant associations are established for each plasmid in the T7 RNAP variant library using long-read nanopore sequencing. Variant libraries are then introduced into the GROQ-seq T7 RNAP experimental pipeline (Fig. 1), which consists of three main phases*:

1. T7 RNAP Pooled Growth-Based Assay
2. DNA extraction⁸
3. T7 RNAP BarSeq Preparation and Pooling

**For an in-depth description of each phase, including protocols, required reagents, consumables, and hardware, see the respective files in the Supplemental Materials for reference.*

After these three phases are complete, the pooled samples are sent for Illumina sequencing, and resulting sequencing reads are analyzed using our computational pipeline. To access the complete computational pipeline for analyzing these experiments go to:

<https://github.com/Align-to-Innovate/groqseq-pipeline>

Figure 1: A high-level overview of the T7 RNAP GROQ-seq experimental pipeline.

Measurement Strain

We expressed each T7 RNAP variant from a circuit-bearing plasmid transformed into *E. coli* DH10B. DH10B was chosen for this T7 RNAP dataset due to its high transformation efficiency and widespread use in synthetic biology. This strain can be accessed from New England Biolabs (Ipswich, MA).

Circuit Design

The T7 RNAP GROQ-seq assay employs a genetic circuit connecting T7 RNAP function to growth using an antibiotic resistance gene as a selection marker (Fig. 2). In the circuit, T7 RNAP is constitutively expressed. The T7 promoter regulates transcription of a bicistronic operon containing mScarlet and murine dihydrofolate reductase (mDHFR), which confers trimethoprim (TMP) resistance. mScarlet expression is used to calibrate fitness measurements to T7 RNAP function in singleplex fluorescence assays. High-functioning T7 RNAP variants will express increased levels of mScarlet-I3 and mDHFR, conferring high fluorescence and greater resistance to TMP. In short, higher function leads to more growth. A genbank file for the pT7-78-WT_BasePlasmid, using what was defined as the wild-type (WT) T7 RNAP variant plasmid, can be found in the Supplemental Materials.

Figure 2: The GROQ-seq T7 RNAP assay's plasmid diagram. Illustrating the barcode region, expression cassette, selection cassette, and backbone.

Expression Cassette

The expression cassette contains an operon in which the T7 RNAP protein sequence is constitutively expressed in the opposite orientation to the genes in the selection cassette (Fig. 2). A self-cleaving ribozyme normalizes the 5' mRNA transcript end, and a bicistronic design (BCD) element stabilizes translation across T7 RNAP variants. The promoter and BCD element were selected to tune T7 RNAP calibration variants with known activities, enabling clear resolution between low- and high-functioning variants^{9,10}.

Selection Cassette

The selection cassette is bicistronic, containing a class III T7 promoter to express mScarlet and mDHFR (Fig. 2). T7 RNAP binds to the T7 promoter upstream of the mScarlet gene and drives the production of the mScarlet-DHFR operon. Like the expression cassette, a self-cleaving ribozyme normalizes the 5' mRNA transcript end. Each RBS was tuned separately for mScarlet and mDHFR to enable clear resolution across variants for both function and fitness.

Barcode Region

This plasmid utilizes a dual barcode system to create a vast diversity of barcodes, enabling each protein variant to be uniquely identified, often with multiple barcodes per variant. The system consists of two barcode halves separated by a homology region, where each of the barcode halves takes the form NNNWSNNNWSNNNWSNNNWSNNNWSNNNWSNNN. For additional information about the barcoding strategy please refer to the GROQ-seq Platform Proposal (section 4.2.1: Barcode Region)¹¹.

Backbone

The backbone used for variant libraries in this work is pTwist Kan Medium Copy from Twist Biosciences (South San Francisco, CA). This backbone contains a p15A origin of replication and a kanamycin resistance marker.

Control Plasmids

Base Library Plasmids

The GenBank file for the T7 RNAP base library plasmid (Table 1) is included in the Supplemental Materials. This uses what was defined as the wild-type (WT) variant of T7 RNAP. This plasmid includes annotations for circuit components as well as the parts used in Golden Gate cloning.

Calibration and Normalization Plasmids

Both calibration and normalization variant controls were used in this assay (Table 1), and their GenBank files can be found in the Supplemental Materials. These control variants enable the conversion of sequencing-based fitness into quantitative functional values (for more details see the GROQ-seq platform proposalⁱⁱ, section 8: Data Analysis and Machine Learning Evaluation).

Two well-characterized normalization variants, previously developed for the GROQ-seq Transcription Factor (TF) Assay, were used alongside an additional mDHFR variant to function as ‘always-high’ variants. The similarity of assay conditions between the TF and T7 RNAP GROQ-seq assays enabled calibration variants not requiring inducers or ligands to be shared between these assays.

Table 1: GROQ-seq T7 RNAP assay plasmids

Name	Variant Description
pT7-78-WT_BasePlasmid	T7 RNAP Base Library Plasmid
pRamR-norm-02	Normalization Variant
pLacI-norm-02	Normalization Variant
pNorm-mDFHR-03	Normalization Variant
pT7-78-WT	Calibration variant 1
pT7-78-E207K	Calibration variant 2
pT7-78-N748D	Calibration variant 3
pT7-78-D240G	Calibration variant 4
pT7-78-D240E	Calibration variant 5
pT7-78-P266L	Calibration variant 6
pT7-78-F21Y	Calibration variant 7

Experimental Design

Selection Marker

This assay is challenged by trimethoprim (TMP) at the following concentrations

- 0ug/mL
- 3ug/uL

Plate map

The T7 RNAP variant libraries were assayed in a 96-well plate format (Fig. 3). The library was tested under two TMP concentrations with each condition represented by four replicate rows of wells. The conditions remained constant across each of the 12 columns, resulting in 48 replicate wells per condition.

Figure 3: The GROQ-seq T7 RNAP assay plate map.

Dataset Description

The initial dataset collected by GROQ-seq T7 RNAP assay is publicly accessible through our data portal (data.alignbio.org), enabling direct access, reuse, and integration with other protein function datasets. This dataset was collected at the Design, Automation, Manufacturing, and Processes (DAMP) Laboratory at Boston University.

Variant Library Overview & Synthesis

This data release includes data for two different types of libraries:

- Site-Saturation Variant Library (SSVL): a library consisting of variants with all possible single-amino-acid substitutions. The SSVL library was purchased from Twist Bioscience (South San Francisco, California). The quality control report for the SSVL library can be found as in the Supplemental Materials.
 - 31 positions were missing from the gene library synthesis used for the SVL libraries. Those missing positions are L37, E48, P100, T101, A102, P111, K164, N165, V166, K172, R173, V186, R215, C216, H230, Q324, A338, A413, K450, I489, L550, L582, L611, G645, D770, S776, V783, D812, S838, C839, and L842.
 - Overall, this dataset covers 76% of the possible single amino acid substitutions.
- Error-prone PCR (epPCR): a library generated using epPCR amplification of the T7 RNAP coding sequence, with a mean non-synonymous mutation coding sequence of 13 mutations per variant in the epPCR library. This median mutation count for the epPCR library was higher than anticipated (initial target was four mutations per variant). The epPCR library was purchased from GenScript USA Inc. (Piscataway, NJ).

Cloning & Transformation

Protein variant libraries and random barcodes were cloned into the GROQ-seq T7 RNAP backbone plasmid using a 6-part Golden Gate assembly. This process was performed by Clutch Biotechnologies (Burlingame, California). The parts designed for Golden Gate assembly can be found as annotations in the T7 RNAP base plasmid with the category labeled 'Clutch'. All libraries were first cloned in NEB® 10-beta Competent E. coli (c3019-DH10B) from New England Biolabs (Ipswich, MA) before being run through the GROQ-seq platform.

Barcode Mapping

In order to map variant sequences to their unique barcodes, long-read sequencing was performed on all variant libraries. Long-read sequencing was performed by Plasmidsaurus (South San Francisco, CA).

Sequencing

For all samples coming out of the GROQ-seq T7 RNAP assay, enrichment of each variant was determined by sequencing the number of barcodes present via short-read sequencing. Samples were sent to Novogene (Sacramento, CA) for barcode sequencing. All samples were sequenced with a 25B-read flow cell.

Data Analysis

This dataset includes measurements for 34,000 T7 RNAP variants, including more than 12,000 single- and 21,000 multi-residue mutants. To access the complete computational pipeline used to analyze these experiments go to:

<https://github.com/Align-to-Innovate/groqseq-pipeline>. For additional specific information about data analysis and cleaning, please refer to the README attached as a supplemental download at <https://data.alignbio.org/>.

Barcode Quality Sieve

Table 2. Barcode quality sieve – T7RNAP libraries (T7RNAP–SVL and T7RNAP–epPCR)

Sequential quality filters applied to the T7RNAP–SVL and T7RNAP–epPCR libraries. Steps Start–1 show combined counts as per-library assignment is not available at those stages. Per-library counts are first available at step 2. Steps 3–6 were applied to the combined dataset. Percentage retained for the final row is relative to step 2 counts.

Filter		T7RNAP–SVL			T7RNAP–epPCR		
Step	Description	Remaining	Removed	% Retained	Remaining	Removed	% Retained
Start	Initial barcode dataset All barcodes from Bartender clustering with ≥50 reads in at least one sample	256,997 – per-library counts not available at this stage					
1	Exclude reference sequence spike-ins Spike-in controls with known sequences are retained separately for fitness calibration. Reference sequence barcodes are not assigned to either library.	256,987 (10 removed) – per-library counts not available at this stage					
2	High-confidence protein sequence required Each barcode must have a reliable consensus coding sequence from Nanopore long reads: ≥60% of reads must agree on one sequence, or multi-sequence alignment quality ≥30 at every base. Frame-shifted sequences are excluded. Per-library counts are first available at this step.	54,282	-	100.0%	67,799	-	100.0%
3	Plasmid length matches expected size Modal Nanopore read length must fall within the expected range for an intact 6,991 bp plasmid. Barcodes with reads that are too long are presumed to carry backbone insertions; those with reads that are too short are presumed to carry deletions. The lower bound relaxes at low read depth where length estimates are less reliable (see note a),	85,899 (36,182 removed, 70.4% of step 2 retained) – combined SVL + epPCR only					

Filter		T7RNAP-SVL			T7RNAP-epPCR		
Step	Description	Remaining	Removed	% Retained	Remaining	Removed	% Retained
4	Fitness values are non-null Each barcode must have non-missing fitness values across all 36 fitness parameters	84,972 (927 removed, 69.6% of step 2 retained) - combined SVL + epPCR only					
5	All backbone elements present Every backbone element must be covered by the expected number of reads, typically between 0.5 and 0.7 times the total number of Nanopore reads for the barcode, with a relaxed threshold at lower read count to allow for Poisson sampling errors. Elements checked include the kanamycin resistance cassette, p15a origin of replication, DHFR ribosome binding sites, T7 promoter regulatory region, mScarlet fluorescent marker and its regulatory region, and two transcription terminators (see note b).	82,696 (2,276 removed, 67.7% of step 2 retained) - combined SVL + epPCR only					
6	Backbone element sequences are correct When critical backbone elements are sequenced with high confidence, they must exactly match the expected reference sequence: the DHFR gene and ribosome binding site, T7 promoter regulatory region, mScarlet regulatory region, and p15a origin of replication. Barcodes where a checked element is present but sequenced at low confidence are retained (see note c).	81,121 (1,575 removed, 66.4% of step 2 retained) - combined SVL + epPCR only					
Final	Clean dataset	41,979	12,303	77.3%	39,142	28,657	57.7%

Overall retention (steps 2–6): T7RNAP-SVL: 41,979 / 54,282 barcodes retained (77.3%) T7RNAP-epPCR: 39,142 / 67,799 barcodes retained (57.7%)

Filter definitions

(a) Plasmid length. The modal Nanopore read length must fall within expected bounds for an intact 6,991 bp plasmid. The upper bound is strict: reads longer than 6,998 bp (0.1% above the expected length) are excluded, as these are presumed to carry backbone insertions. The lower bound is read-depth dependent: a barcode is retained if its modal read length divided by the expected plasmid length exceeds $0.98 - 0.6/n$, where n is the Nanopore read count per barcode. At high read depth this threshold approaches 98% of the expected length (6,851 bp); at low read depth it relaxes, because length estimates from few reads are less reliable. Barcodes with reads that are too short are presumed to carry backbone deletions.

(b) Backbone elements. The 12 elements checked are: kanamycin resistance cassette (two regions), p15a origin of replication (two regions), DHFR and associated ribosome binding site (two regions), T7 promoter regulatory region, mScarlet fluorescent marker (two regions), mScarlet regulatory region, and two transcription terminators (ECK12 spy terminator and L3S2P00 terminator). For barcodes with ≥ 8 Nanopore reads, the observed count for each element must exceed the threshold $(n - 8)\alpha - \sqrt{(n - 8)\alpha}$, where n is the Nanopore read count per barcode

and α is an element-specific slope fitted from the 5th percentile of observed count-to-read-depth ratios across all barcodes. Barcodes with fewer than 8 reads are exempt from this filter. Barcodes where a required element is absent from all reads are presumed to carry a plasmid rearrangement or assembly failure.

(c) Backbone sequence correctness. The five elements checked are the DHFR ribosome binding site (two regions), T7 promoter regulatory region, mScarlet regulatory region, and p15a origin of replication. Sequence checking is applied only when the element is covered at high confidence ($\geq 60\%$ of reads must agree on one sequence, or multi-sequence alignment quality ≥ 30 at every base); barcodes where an element is present but covered at low confidence are retained rather than excluded. Barcodes where a checked element does not match the reference are presumed to carry a backbone mutation that could affect plasmid function independently of the gene of interest.

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